

Research Article

Content and Distribution of Heavy Metals in an Abandoned Mechanic and Non-Mechanic Sites in Abakaliki, Southeastern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was carried out to determine and compare the depth content and distribution of heavy metals in abandoned mechanic and non-mechanic sites in Abakaliki Southeastern Nigeria. Soil samples were collected from a pit at 0 – 20 cm, 20 – 40 cm, 40 – 60 cm and 60 – 80 cm depth in each sites and analysed for Hg, Pb, Fe and Cd. The results showed that abandoned mechanic site recorded higher contents of the heavy metals studied than non-mechanic site. Lead, Fe and Cd were within the normal range in the two sites studied while Hg where above the normal in ranged in all the sites studied. Similarly, apart from Hg which increased with an increase in depth in the two sites studied, all the other heavy metals did not show any fixed pattern of distribution with depth. From the results, abandoned mechanic site is a source of heavy metals in the soil and care should be taking while working in such sites to avoid contacting health problems associated to heavy metals.

Key Words: Depth, heavy metals, mechanic site, pit and toxic

INTRODUCTION

The term heavy metal refers to any metallic element that has a relatively high density ($>4 \text{ gcm}^{-3}$) and is toxic or poisonous at low concentration. Examples are Mercury (Hg), Cadmium (Cd), Arsenic (As), Chromium (Cr), Lead (Pb) and Zinc (Zn) (Njoku and Ayoka, 2007). These metals are natural components of the earth's crust and cannot be degraded or destroyed. As trace elements, some heavy metals (e.g. copper, selenium, zinc) are essential for maintaining the metabolism of human body. However, at higher concentration they can lead to poisoning. Heavy metal poisoning could result from drinking contaminated water (e.g. lead pipes), high ambient air concentrations near emission sources or intake through the food chain. With the increase in heavy metal contamination of the soil, it is possible to degrade the soil to such an extent that it becomes useless, harmful and even deadly (Radojevic and Bashjin, 1999). Heavy metals are dangerous because they tend to bioaccumulate. Compounds accumulate in living things anytime they are taken up and stored faster than they are broken down (metabolized) or excreted. These metals can enter a water supply through industrial and consumer waste, or even from acidic rain breaking down soils and releasing heavy metals into streams, lakes, rivers, and groundwater. Over the years, there has been increased public awareness of potential dangers of heavy metals to the ecosystem and in particular to human health (Meilor, 2001).

Soil heavy metals are found in a variety of physio-chemical forms and these include:

- a) Free or complex ions in soil solution
- b) Adsorbed cations at soil micelles
- c) Presence in the lattice of secondary minerals such as phosphate, sulphides or carbonates
- d) Presence in the amorphous materials such as Fe and Mn oxyhydroxides, sulphides or organic matter
- e) Presence in the crystal lattices of primary mineral (Drever, 1997)

Reports on content and distribution of heavy metals (Hg, Cd, Fe, Pb) are few in the study. Therefore, the objective of this study is to determine and compare the depth content and distribution of heavy metals in abandoned mechanic and non-mechanic sites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Site

The experiment was carried out in 2010 at abandoned mechanic and non-mechanic sites in Abakaliki. The area is located at latitude $6^{\circ} 19' N$ and longitude $8^{\circ} 06' E$ in the derived savannah of the southeast agro-ecological zone of Nigeria (Figure 1). It has a mean annual rainfall of 1700 – 1800 mm. The rainfall pattern is bimodal between April – July and September – November with short spell in August. The minimum and maximum temperatures of the area are $27^{\circ}C$ and $31^{\circ}C$ respectively. The relative humidity of the area is between 60 – 80 %. The soil belongs to the order Ultisol and is classified as Typic Haplustult (FDALR, 1985).

Field Methods

A reconnaissance survey of the study site was carried out and abandoned mechanic site at Spera-deo, Abakaliki and non-mechanic site at Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture and Natural Resources Management (FARM), Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki were chosen. Three pits were dug on each site and representative soil samples were taken from 0 – 20 cm, 20 – 40 cm, 40 – 60 cm and 60 – 80 cm from each pit. Thus, treatments are pit A (soil sample from abandoned mechanic site) and pit B (soil sample from non-mechanic site). Soil samples collected were air-dried for three days, sieved using a 2 mm sieve, labelled and taken to laboratory for determination of heavy metals (Hg, Cd, Fe and Pb).

Laboratory Determination

The heavy metals (Hg, Cd, Fe and Pb) content were determined from the soil sample using atomic absorption spectrophotometer after digestion with concentrated HNO_3 (Alloway, 1996)

Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using coefficient of variance (Steel and Torrie, 1980).

RESULTS

The results of the heavy metals contents of the studied sites are shown in Table 1. At 0 – 20 cm depth abandon mechanic site recorded the Hg content of 0.23 MgKg^{-1} . This observed Hg content of abandon mechanic site at 0 – 20 cm was higher than that of non-mechanic site by 22%. Non-mechanic site had the lower mercury content than abandon mechanic site at 20 – 40 cm depth. Similarly, at 40 – 60 cm depth the order of increase of Hg was abandon mechanic site > Non-mechanic site. At 60 – 80 cm, abandon mechanic sites recorded the Hg content of 1.15 MgKg^{-1} . This observed value at 60 – 80 cm depth was higher than that non-mechanic site by 39%. With respect to Hg content of the two sites studied, there was an increase of Hg content with depth.

The order of Pb increase at 0 – 20 cm depth was abandon mechanic site > than that non-mechanic site. At 20 – 40 cm depth abandon mechanic site had the Pb content of 35.50 MgKg^{-1} while that of non-mechanic site was 6.20 MgKg^{-1} . Abandon mechanic site recorded Pb content of 28.90 MgKg^{-1} at 40 – 60 cm depth. This Pb content at 40 – 60 cm depth of abandon mechanic site was higher than that of non-mechanic site by 57%. Similarly, at depth of 60 – 80 cm abandon mechanic and non-mechanic sites recorded the Pb values of 33.10 and 19.85 MgKg^{-1} , respectively. Unlike, Hg content there was no fixed pattern of distribution of Pb content with an increase in depth in the two sites studied.

Table 1: Heavy metals contents of the soil studied

Heavy Metal	Depth (cm)	Pit A (MgKg ⁻¹)	Pit B (MgKg ⁻¹)
Hg	0 – 20	0.23	0.18
	20 – 40	0.65	0.38
	40 – 60	1.00	0.56
	60 – 80	1.15	0.70
	CV (%)	54	50
Pb	0 – 20	28.94	17.84
	20 – 40	35.50	6.20
	40 – 60	28.90	12.35
	60 – 80	33.10	19.85
	CV (%)	10	44
Fe	0 – 20	22.15	19.60
	20 – 40	28.90	16.98
	40 – 60	27.38	15.70
	60 – 80	24.68	12.90
	CV (%)	12	17
Cd	0 – 20	0.75	0.60
	20 – 40	0.70	0.55
	40 – 60	1.20	0.95
	60 – 80	1.55	0.70
	CV (%)	38	25

*Pit A = Abandon mechanic site

Pit B = Non-mechanic site

Abandon mechanic site recorded Cd value of 0.75 MgKg⁻¹ at 0 – 20 cm depth. This Cd value recorded at 0 – 20 cm depth in abandon mechanic site was higher than that of non-mechanic site by 20%. At 20 – 40 cm the order of increase in Cd was abandon mechanic site higher than non-mechanic site. Abandon mechanic and non-mechanic sites recorded the Cd values of 1.20 and 0.95 MgKg⁻¹, respectively at 40 – 60 cm depth. At 60 – 80 cm depth abandon mechanic site recorded Cd value of 1.55 MgKg⁻¹. This observed value of Cd at 60 – 80 cm depth in abandon mechanic site was higher than that of non-mechanic site by 55.

Table 2 shows the pit mean and range of Hg, Pb, Fe and Cd contents of the studied sites. The pit mean Hg values of the sites studied were 0.76 and 0.46 MgKg⁻¹ for abandon mechanic and non-mechanic sites respectively. While Hg ranged between 0.23 – 1.15 MgKg⁻¹ and 0.18 – 0.70 MgKg⁻¹ for abandon mechanic and non-mechanic sites, respectively. Abandon mechanic site recorded Pb pit mean and range of 31.63 MgKg⁻¹ and 28.90 – 35.50 MgKg⁻¹, respectively. Whereas Pb pit mean and range in the non-mechanic site were 14.06 MgKg⁻¹ and 6.20 – 19.85 MgKg⁻¹, respectively. The pit mean and range value of Fe in abandon mechanic site were 25.78 MgKg⁻¹ and 22.15 – 28.90 MgKg⁻¹ while that of non-mechanic site were 16.30 MgKg⁻¹ and 12.90 – 19.60 MgKg⁻¹, respectively. The Cd pit mean content were 1.05 MgKg⁻¹ and 0.70 MgKg⁻¹ for abandon mechanic and non-mechanic sites while Cd in them ranged between 0.70 – 1.15 MgKg⁻¹ and 0.55 – 0.95 MgKg⁻¹, respectively.

DISCUSSIONS

The heavy metals content of abandon mechanic and non-mechanic sites varied as shown in Table 1. Table 1 also showed that abandoned mechanic site recorded higher values of heavy metals than non-mechanic site. Anikwe and Nwobodo (2002) and Okonkwo et al. (2011) reported increase in heavy metals in dumpsite than non-dumpsite. Similarly, Mbah et al. (2011) observed increase in heavy metals in plots treated with organic wastes. Languard (1999) has shown that areas that experience intense human activities like mechanic site are likely to have higher heavy metals than non-mechanic site. The results of the study also showed that apart from Hg that increased with an increase in pit depth, Pb, Fe and Cd do not showed any fixed pattern of distribution. Nyanagababo and Hamaya (1986) reported that surface soils are better indicators for metallic content in the soils than sub soil which is not in agreement with this study.

Table 2: Pit mean and range of heavy metals studied (MgKg^{-1})

Pit Identification	Hg		Pb		Fe		Cd	
	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range
Pit A	0.76	0.23 – 1.15	31.63	28.90 – 35.50	25.78	22.15 – 28.90	1.05	0.70 – 1.55
Pit B	0.46	0.18 – 0.70	14.06	6.20 – 19.85	16.30	12.90 – 19.60	0.70	0.55 – 0.95

*Pit A = Abandon mechanic site

Pit B = Non-mechanic site

According to Alloway (1996) normal range for Hg, Pb and Cd in the soil are 0.01 – 0.05, 2 – 300 and 0.01 – 20 MgKg^{-1} , respectively. With the exception of Hg content, the values of the heavy metals in the two sites studied were within the normal range in the soil.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study showed that abandoned mechanic site recorded higher values of heavy metals studied than non-mechanic site. Although, with the exception of Hg content which are above the normal range in the soil, all other heavy metal studied were within the normal range. With this, it can be infer that abandoned mechanic site is a source of heavy metals and caution should be taken while working in such site to avoid the health problems associated with heavy metals.

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